

Studies on the Condensation of Sodium Hydroxy Methane Sulphonate with Active Methylene Compounds

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Number of bis-(cyanacetarylamides) and Sulphomethylated acetoacetarylamides have been obtained using sodium hydroxymethane sulphonate.

Compounds containing reactive methylene group and those with active hydrogen, on reaction with sodium hydroxy methane sulphonate, under suitable conditions, lead to the formation of methylene bis-derivatives and sulphomethylated products.^{1,2,3}

In continuation of early studies^{4,5}, cyanacetarylamides and acetoacetarylamides were respectively condensed with sodium hydroxymethane sulphonate (OHCH₂SO₃Na) and the former gave corresponding bis-derivatives (I); while the latter, in presence of a trace of catalyst (KCN), gave sulphomethylated products (II) as under :

(where R = Phenyl, tolyl, xylyl or naphthyl groups).

EXPERIMENTAL

(a) *Methylene-bis-cyanacetanilide* : Cyanacetanilide (0.02M) was dissolved in 90% methanol to which was added solution of sodium hydroxymethane sulphonate (0.01M) in 5 ml. of water. The reaction mixture was refluxed on sandbath for 3 hrs., and 50 ml. of water were added to it at room temperature. The resulting product was then filtered and crystallised from acetic acid in white crystals. In the same way methylene-bis-compounds listed in Table 1 are obtained.

TABLE I

(M = Methylene-bis-cyanacet)

Sr. No.	Compound	Molecular formula	M.P. °C*	Yield %	%Nitrogen		%Carbon		%Hydrogen	
					Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1.	M-anilide	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄	285	45.4	16.43	16.86	68.59	68.66	4.45	4.85
2.	M- <i>o</i> -chloroanilide	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₂	241	35.0	14.18	13.97	—	—	—	—
3.	M- <i>p</i> -chloroanilide	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₂	226	40.0	13.63	13.97	—	—	—	—
4.	M- <i>o</i> -toluidide	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₄	240	44.4	15.90	15.55	—	—	—	—
5.	M- <i>m</i> -toluidide	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₄	212	47.2	15.92	15.55	—	—	—	—
6.	M- <i>p</i> -toluidide	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₄	220	44.0	15.86	15.55	69.80	69.98	5.80	5.59
7.	M- <i>o</i> -anisidide	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₄	260	42.1	14.14	14.28	—	—	—	—
8.	M-1 : 2 : 4-xylydide	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₄	256	41.0	14.90	14.42	70.91	71.11	6.11	6.23
9.	M-1 : 3 : 4-xylydide	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₄	266	38.4	14.96	14.42	—	—	—	—
10.	M- α -naphthylamide.	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₄	236	41.8	13.20	12.96	—	—	—	—
11.	M- β -naphthylamide.	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₄	227	46.5	12.62	12.96	—	—	—	—

* All melting points are uncorrected.

(b) *Sodium acetoacetanilide methane sulphonate* : Acetoacetanilide (0.01M) was dissolved in ethanol (10 ml.) to which an aqueous solution (2 ml.) of sodium hydroxymethane sulphonate (0.01M), in presence of a trace of potassium cyanide as catalyst, was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed on sand bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr., during which time the voluminous precipitates were obtained. It was then filtered and the product was crystallised from water in white shining needles. In the same way sulphonated compounds listed in Table 2 are obtained.

TABLE 2

(S = Sodium acetoacet-) (M = methane sulphonate)

Sr. No.	Compound	Molecular formula	M.P. °C*	Yield %	%Nitrogen		%Sulphur	
					Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1.	S-anilide-M	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₅ NSNa	300	53.23	4.43	4.74	—	—
2.	S- <i>o</i> -chloroanilide-M	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₅ NSClNa	195	44.35	4.29	4.28	—	—
3.	S- <i>m</i> -chloroanilide-M	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₅ NSClNa	300	51.99	4.10	4.28	—	—
4.	S- <i>p</i> -chloroanilide-M	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₅ NSClNa	300	45.87	4.37	4.28	—	—
5.	S- <i>o</i> -toluidide-M	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₅ NSNa	235	55.38	4.61	4.56	—	—
6.	S- <i>p</i> -toluidide-M	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₅ NSNa	300	53.75	4.28	4.56	10.73	10.42
7.	S- <i>o</i> -anisidide-M	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₅ NSNa	270	47.98	4.16	4.33	—	—
8.	S- <i>p</i> -phenitidide-M	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₅ NSNa	300	55.20	3.83	4.12	9.92	9.50
9.	S-1 : 2 : 4-xylydide-M	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₅ NSNa	205	56.08	4.45	4.36	—	—
10.	S-1 : 3 : 4-xylydide-M	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₅ NSNa	196	54.50	4.17	4.36	—	—
11.	S- α -naphthylamide-M	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₅ NSNa	230	58.30	3.94	4.08	—	—
12.	S- β -naphthylamide-M	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₅ NSNa	300	56.71	4.00	4.08	9.80	9.33

* All melting points are uncorrected.

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